

A dual approach using PEGylated nanocarriers and microneedles to enhance transdermal delivery of macromolecular proteins from goat placenta extract

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Abstract

Goat placenta (GP) extract contains bioactive macromolecules that stimulate skin cell growth; however, the transdermal delivery of hydrophilic macromolecules remains limited. This study aimed to develop PEGylated nanocarriers combined with microneedles (MN) as a transdermal delivery approach for macromolecular proteins from GP extract. PEGylated liposomes (P-LI) and PEGylated nanoparticles (P-NP) were formulated to entrap GP extract and subsequently combined with MN patches. *In vitro* permeation studies and pathway visualization were conducted using bovine serum albumin–fluorescein isothiocyanate (BSA-FITC) as a model protein. The GP extract-loaded P-LI exhibited the highest protein entrapment efficiency, uniform nanovesicle formation, narrow size distribution, and negative surface charge, making it the optimal candidate for MN loading. The P-LI-loaded MN system enhanced both skin permeation and dermal deposition of the macromolecular proteins, resulting in their accumulation in the deeper skin layers. In conclusion, the P-LI–MN system provides an effective platform for the transdermal delivery of hydrophilic macromolecules from GP extract.

Keywords

goat placenta, macromolecular protein, microneedles, PEGylated liposomes, PEGylated nanoparticles, transdermal delivery

Introduction

Goat placenta (GP) is renowned for its richness in hydrophilic macromolecular proteins and growth factors (e.g., epidermal growth factor (EGF), fibroblast growth factor (FGF), insulin-like growth factor-1 (IGF-1), transforming growth factor- β 1 (TGF- β 1)), as well as amino acids. These bioactive constituents have demonstrated potent proliferative, migratory, and regenerative effects on dermal cells (Tansathien et al. 2022). Exogenous proteins and growth factors are increasingly explored for their potential in regenerative medicine, offering promising avenues for cell, tissue, and organ repair (Mao and Mooney 2015; Ren et al. 2020). Additionally, amino acids stimulate fibroblasts, boost collagen production, and reduce pigmentation (Pan et al. 2017). The transdermal and transfollicular delivery of hydrophilic macromolecules is constrained by the architectural and physicochemical barriers posed by the skin structure (Bolzinger et al. 2012). For skin rejuvenation and revitalization, placenta extract can be administered through mesotherapy or topical application, complementing various cosmeceutical aesthetic procedures (El-Domyati et al. 2012). Hypodermic injections are associated with pain, the generation of hazardous medical waste, and the risk of disease transmission due to needle reuse (Miller and Pisani 1999). In contrast, self-administered transdermal delivery systems offer a cost-effective alternative that can improve patient compliance (Prausnitz and Langer 2008).

Liposomes, lipid-based nanocarriers, serve as a promising delivery system for various therapeutic molecular compounds into the skin and follicular regions (Pierre and dos Santos Miranda Costa 2011). The modification of liposomal membrane surfaces with hydrophilic polymers, such as polyethylene glycol (PEG) 2000, enhances colloidal stability and augments the skin permeability of hydrophilic compounds (Rangsimawong et al. 2018). Polymeric nanoparticles have also been investigated for dermal and transdermal drug delivery systems (Patzelt 2017); however, the passive diffusion of protein-based therapeutics across the skin remains a significant challenge (Chaulagain et al. 2018).

Among various surface modification strategies, PEGylation was selected due to its well-documented ability to enhance colloidal stability, prolong systemic and local bioavailability, and impart a “stealth” characteristic that reduces recognition and clearance by the mononuclear phagocyte system (MPS). PEG provides a universal and biocompatible hydrophilic shield that minimizes aggregation and promotes deeper skin penetration of macromolecules (Knudsen et al. 2012; Suk et al. 2016). This makes PEGylated nanocarriers particularly advantageous for the transdermal delivery of hydrophilic proteins and growth factors, where stability and stealth behavior are critical for maintaining therapeutic efficacy.

Apart from passive permeation strategies, microneedling is a minimally invasive technique that facilitates direct drug delivery across the stratum corneum – the primary barrier of the skin – thereby enhancing skin per-

meability for various compounds (Prausnitz and Langer 2008; Kim et al. 2012; Ma and Wu 2017; Ye et al. 2018; Jung and Jin 2021). By creating transient microchannels that bypass the stratum corneum, microneedles have the potential to deliver macromolecular proteins into the skin and hair follicles (Tansathien et al. 2022). Furthermore, the combination of highly efficient physical methods with diverse nanocarriers has demonstrated superior drug penetration enhancement, surpassing the efficacy of their individual use (Dragicevic and Maibach 2018; Yu et al. 2021). Chitosan-based liposomes encapsulating bioactive macromolecules from deer antler velvet extract, in combination with microsized needles in serum, demonstrated effective delivery through both skin and hair penetration routes (Rangsimawong et al. 2024a). Similarly, nanionosomes encapsulating deer placenta extract, combined with a microspicule gel, were successfully utilized as a transfollicular delivery system to promote hair regeneration (Rangsimawong et al. 2024b). More recently, PEG-grafted liposomes incorporated into a microspicule-based gel were reported to enhance both transdermal and transfollicular delivery of macromolecular proteins and GP extract (Sanguanboonyaphong et al. 2024). Despite these advances, no study has yet investigated the synergistic integration of PEGylated nanocarriers with a microneedle (MN) patch for the delivery of bioactive macromolecules from GP extract.

This study aimed to develop PEGylated nanocarriers combined with MN as a transdermal delivery approach for macromolecular proteins from GP extract. To improve macromolecular skin permeability, PEGylated nanocarriers loaded with GP extract were prepared and incorporated into MN patches. *In vitro* skin permeation and deposition studies were conducted to determine the effects of nano- and micro-formulations. The penetration mechanism was also evaluated using confocal laser scanning microscopy (CLSM). We hypothesize that the synergistic integration of PEGylated nanocarriers with MN will overcome the skin's barrier properties, thereby enhancing the transdermal permeation and deposition of hydrophilic macromolecules from GP extract more effectively than either strategy alone.

Materials and methods

Materials

GP extract was obtained from the Faculty of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Ubon Ratchathani University. Its composition was previously quantified, showing a high protein content (705.51 mg/g) with substantial levels of FGF, IGF-1, EGF, and TGF- β 1 (Tansathien et al. 2022).

Egg phosphatidylcholine (PC) and N-(carbonyl-methoxypolyethyleneglycol-2000)-1,2-distearoyl-*sn*-glycero-3-phosphoethanolamine sodium salt (PEG2000-DSPE) were kindly provided by Lipoid GmbH (Ludwigshafen, Germany). Cholesterol (Chol) was purchased from Carlo Erba Reagents (Ronato, Italy), and

polysorbate 20 (Tween 20) was obtained from the Namsiang Group (Bangkok, Thailand). Lissamine rhodamine B 1,2-dihexadecanoyl-*sn*-glycero-3-phosphoethanolamine triethylammonium salt (Rh) was sourced from Invitrogen (Carlsbad, CA, USA). Bovine serum albumin-fluorescein isothiocyanate conjugate (BSA-FITC), sodium tripolyphosphate (TPP), and polyethylene glycol dimethacrylate (PEG dimethacrylate) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich Co. (MO, USA). Chitosan (molecular weight 8,000 g/mol) was obtained from OliZac Technologies Co., Ltd. (Bangkok, Thailand), and PEG2000 was acquired from Tokyo Chemical Industry Co., Ltd. (Tokyo, Japan). Hyaluronic acid was sourced from the P.C. Drug Center (Bangkok, Thailand). All other chemicals were of analytical grade.

Development of PEGylated nanocarriers loading GP extract

Polymer-modified liposomes were formulated as lipid nanocarriers for the dermal delivery of macromolecules. Surface modification of the liposomes with conjugated PEG2000 was conducted to entrap macromolecular proteins from the extract. A liposome formulation containing PC, Chol, and PEG2000–DSPE at a ratio of 10:2:0.12 mM was prepared using the thin-film hydration and sonication method (Rangsimawong et al. 2016). Briefly, a mixture of lipid components was dissolved in chloroform:methanol (2:1, v/v) within a test tube. The organic solvents were evaporated under a stream of nitrogen gas to form a thin lipid film, which was subsequently dried in a desiccator for 6 hours. The dried lipid film was then hydrated with a solution of 0.2% (w/v) GP extract dissolved in phosphate-buffered saline (PBS, pH 7.4) containing 2% (w/v) polysorbate 20. This mixture was sonicated in an ice bath for 30 minutes using a probe sonicator to reduce the liposomal vesicle size. Centrifugation was then carried out to eliminate excess lipid components, and the supernatant was stored at 40 °C until further use.

Surface-modified polymeric nanocarriers were also prepared to entrap hydrophilic macromolecules of the extract. Briefly, chitosan and PEG2000 were dissolved in 1% (v/v) hydrochloric acid (HCl), while TPP was dissolved in water. The 0.2% (w/v) GP extract was mixed with the chitosan solution. The TPP solution was dropped into the chitosan solution at a pump rate of 0.15 times/min with probe sonication at a rate of 30 min/cycle on ice. The nanoparticles were continually sonicated on ice for 30 minutes to reduce their size, after which their physicochemical properties were characterized.

Table 1. The compositions of modified nanocarrier formulations.

Formulations	PC (%)	Chol (%)	PEG2000–DSPE (%)	Chitosan (%)	TPP (%)	PEG2000 (%)
Liposomes (LI)	0.773	0.077	-	-	-	-
PEGylated liposomes (P-LI)	0.773	0.077	0.030	-	-	-
Nanoparticles (NP)	-	-	-	0.500	0.250	-
PEGylated nanoparticles (P-NP)	-	-	-	0.500	0.250	1.000

Characterization of PEGylated nanocarriers loading GP extract

A dynamic light scattering particle size analyzer (Zetasizer Nano-ZS, Malvern Instruments, Worcestershire, UK) was used to determine particle size, size distribution, and surface charge. The formulations were appropriately diluted with water before analysis and measured in triplicate under ambient conditions.

Entrapment efficiency was determined using centrifugal filter tubes (Amicon Ultra Centrifugal Filter, 100kDa MWCO, Merck, USA). A 2 mL sample of the formulation was filled into the filter tube and centrifuged at 4,000 rpm and 4 °C for 15 min. Nanocarriers containing entrapped GP extract were collected from the filter device and mixed with either 0.1% Triton X-100 (1:1, v/v) for lipid-based nanocarriers or 2% HCl for polymeric nanocarriers. Protein content was evaluated using a bicinchoninic acid (BCA) protein assay kit (Novagen, EMD Millipore Corp., USA) according to the manufacturer's instructions. Entrapment efficiency (%EE) was calculated using Equation (1).

$$\%EE = \frac{GP_{extract\ entrapped\ nanocarriers}}{Initial\ GP_{extract\ loaded}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

Formulation of PEGylated nanocarriers combined with MN patch

Microneedle (MN) patches containing 10% (w/w) hyaluronic acid and 0.5% (w/w) PEG dimethacrylate were prepared and mixed with the GP extract-loaded nanocarriers. The micro-molding technique was used to fabricate the MN patches, as previously described (Tansathien et al. 2022). Briefly, the formulations were weighed into a laser-engineered silicone micromold template. The needle tips of the micromolds were filled by centrifuging at 4,000 rpm for 30 min. After drying at room temperature for 2 days, the MN arrays were removed from the molds, and their physical appearance was captured using a Dino-Lite Edge/5MP digital microscope, AM7915 series (Dino-Lite, Hsinchu, Taiwan).

In vitro skin permeation study

Abdominal porcine skins were sourced from intrapartum stillborn animals at a local farm in Sisaket Province, Thailand, with approval from the Investigational Review Board (05/2565/IACUC), Animal Experimentation Ethics Committee, Ubon Ratchathani University. The subcutaneous tissue was carefully removed using surgical scissors. Skin samples with a thickness of approximately 600–700 µm, were stored at –20 °C until further use. Before the experiments, the skin was thawed in PBS (pH 7.4) at room temperature.

The presence of naturally occurring proteins and peptides within the skin can interfere with the precise quantification of externally applied macromolecules. To overcome this limitation, BSA-FITC was employed as a model macromolecular protein in the study (Sanguanboonyaphong et al. 2024). Transdermal permeation was

evaluated using a vertical Franz diffusion cell setup. The receptor chamber was filled with approximately 12 mL of PBS (pH 7.4), maintained at 32 ± 2 °C, and continuously stirred using a magnetic stirrer to ensure uniform distribution. A 0.5 mL volume of the nanocarrier formulation was applied to the skin surface. For the MN application, patches were pressed onto a 2.01 cm² skin area using a constant force of 10 N for 2 minutes. At specific intervals (1, 2, 4, 6, and 8 hours), 0.5 mL of receptor solution was withdrawn for fluorescence measurement and immediately replenished with an equal volume of fresh PBS (pH 7.4) to maintain a consistent volume. All experiments were conducted in triplicate.

After the 8 h skin permeation study, the treated skin samples were gently rinsed with PBS (pH 7.4) to remove any residual formulation from the surface. The skin was then sectioned into small pieces and subjected to extraction in 2 mL of PBS (pH 7.4), followed by sonication in an ultrasonic bath for 30 min. The amount of BSA-FITC deposited within the skin was quantified using fluorescence spectroscopy to assess protein accumulation throughout the tissue.

To quantify the macromolecular protein (BSA-FITC) in each sample, aliquots were transferred into a black 96-well microplate. Fluorescence intensity was measured in triplicate using a fluorescence spectrophotometer (CLARIOstar Plus, BMG LABTECH, Ortenberg, Germany) with excitation and emission wavelengths set at 485 nm and 535 nm, respectively.

CLSM study

In this study, BSA-FITC (a green fluorescent probe) served as a model macromolecular protein, and rhodamine-labeled phospholipid (Rh, a red fluorescent probe) was incorporated to trace the nanocarriers. After 8 h of *in vitro* skin permeation, the skin samples were thoroughly rinsed with PBS (pH 7.4) to eliminate residual formulation. The samples were then immersed in an excess volume of methyl salicylate for optical transparency. A Zeiss LSM 800 confocal laser scanning microscope (Carl Zeiss, Jena, Germany) equipped with diode lasers at 405, 488, and 561 nm was used to visualize the skin surface and permeation depth. Imaging was performed using a 10× objective lens. Fluorescence intensity profiles were analyzed with ZEISS ZEN software by measuring signal intensity along the central horizontal axis of each image. The resulting data were used to generate plots of average fluorescence intensity versus skin depth for each formulation.

Data analysis

Results were expressed as the mean \pm standard deviation (SD). A paired *t*-test was used for the statistical analysis of physicochemical properties. For the skin permeation and deposition studies, a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by Tukey's post hoc test was applied to identify significant differences between groups. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

Results

Nanocarriers loading GP extract

To develop the transdermal delivery system for GP extract, liposomal formulations as lipid nanocarriers and nanoparticles as polymeric nanocarriers were successfully prepared. The physicochemical properties are presented in Fig. 1. All formulations demonstrated nanometer-sized particles with narrow size distributions. The lipid nanocarriers loading GP extract were significantly smaller than the polymeric nanoparticles. Furthermore, PEGylation had a notable impact on particle size: P-NPs were significantly smaller compared with their non-PEGylated counterparts, whereas P-LIs were larger than non-PEGylated liposomes (LI) (Suppl. material 1: table S1). The zeta potential of both LI and P-LI showed a negative surface charge ranging from -19.80 to -21.93 mV, whereas the nanoparticles exhibited a positive charge ranging from $+27.40$ to $+28.97$ mV. For the %EE of the formulations, the order was P-LI > LI > NP > P-NP. Consequently, the P-LI formulation was selected as the nanocarrier for the transdermal delivery of GP extract because of its desirable physical properties and superior loading capacity for macromolecular proteins.

In addition, the morphology of P-LI loading GP extract under atomic force microscopy (AFM) demonstrated a spherical shape with nanometer-sized small unilamellar vesicles (Sanguanboonyaphong et al. 2024). P-LIs also exhibited high physical stability at 4 °C over 90 days. At 25 °C, no significant changes in particle size or PDI were observed during the study period. In contrast, marked instability was observed at 40 °C, where particle size, PDI, and zeta potential changed significantly (Suppl. material 1: table S2). A preliminary investigation also indicated that GP extract-loaded P-LIs retained protein stability in gel-based formulations at 4 °C for up to 90 days (data not shown). These findings support the potential applicability of P-LIs in other formulation platforms.

GP extract-loaded nanocarriers with MN patch

The GP extract-loaded P-LI formulation was successfully incorporated into the MN patch (P-LI MN). Digital microscopy (Fig. 2) revealed the distinctive physical appearance of the hyaluronic acid and PEG dimethacrylate MNs, displaying sharply conical-shaped needle tips (121 needle arrays) with a height of 538.00 ± 7.00 μ m and a base width of 307.33 ± 1.15 μ m. The protein content in the MN patch was 356.04 ± 36.07 μ g per patch. These findings underscore the suitability of the MN patch for loading P-LI as a transdermal delivery system for macromolecules from GP extract.

Skin permeation and deposition

The skin permeation and deposition results, shown in Fig. 3, clearly demonstrate the superior performance of

Figure 1. Physicochemical properties of nanocarriers: (A) size and PDI, (B) zeta potential, and (C) %EE. Data represent average \pm SD ($n = 3$). * indicates a statistically significant difference between formulations ($p < 0.05$).

Figure 2. Appearance and microscopic images of the GP extract-loaded P-LI MN patch (A, B).

the P-LI MN formulation. At all sampling times, the percentage cumulative permeation of BSA-FITC from the P-LI MN was markedly higher than that from the P-LI solution, and P-NP formulations. The percentage of BSA-FITC deposited in the skin from the P-LI MN was also

higher than that of other formulations, with a statistically significant increase compared with the solution form. These findings indicate that the P-LI MN patch effectively enhances the permeability of macromolecular proteins through the skin.

Figure 3. (A) Percent cumulative BSA-FITC permeation–time profiles of solution (×), P-NP (Black up-pointing triangle), P-LI (White circle), and P-LI MN (Black square). (B) Percentage of BSA-FITC deposited in the skin after 8 h of permeation. Data represent the mean \pm standard deviation (SD) ($n = 3$). * indicates a statistically significant difference from the solution ($p < 0.05$).

CLSM

To visualize the skin penetration pathways of P-LI facilitated by microneedling, BSA-FITC, used as a model macromolecular protein, exhibited green fluorescence, while the nanocarriers were tracked via red fluorescence from incorporated rhodamine (Rh-probed nanocarriers), as shown in Fig. 4. In skin samples treated with the P-LI MN patch, microchannels formed by the microneedle array were clearly observed, confirming mechanical disruption of the stratum corneum. X–Y confocal serial images demonstrated the distribution of both fluorescent markers within the skin layers and hair follicles, with penetration depths ranging from 0 μm to 160 μm . Notably, fluorescence intensity was concentrated around the microchannels, indicating localized delivery through the created pathways. The highest intensity of BSA-FITC was observed at a depth of approximately 30 μm , whereas Rh-labeled nanocarriers reached peak fluorescence at around 20 μm .

Discussion

The GP extract presented as a brownish-red, fibrous material and was found to contain various water-soluble compounds, notably high-molecular-weight proteins such as albumin, several growth factors (EGF, FGF, IGF-1, and TGF- β 1), and a range of amino acids (Tansathien et al. 2022). To develop nanocarriers for GP extract, liposomal formulations as lipid nanocarriers and nanoparticles as polymeric nanocarriers were successfully prepared, with the lipid nanocarriers exhibiting smaller particle sizes than the polymeric nanoparticles. Using the sonication

method, the phospholipid bilayer of liposome membranes could be organized into small unilamellar vesicles (size < 100 nm). This preparation results in vesicles with a single phospholipid bilayer encapsulating hydrophilic compounds (Akbarzadeh 2013; Lombardo and Kiselev 2022). For PEGylation, the particle size of P-NP was smaller compared with non-PEGylated nanocarriers, attributed to the strong reduction of attractive (van der Waals) forces and the enhancement of repulsive (steric, electrostatic, and hydration) forces by PEG molecules on the surface (Rangsimawong et al. 2016).

The negative surface charge of both LI and P-LI was attributed to the presence of zwitterionic compounds. This charge arises because the pH (7.4) of the liposome formulations was higher than the typical isoelectric point (pI) of PC, which is around 6–6.7. At a pH above its pI, PC molecules predominantly carry a net negative charge, contributing to the overall negative zeta potential of the liposomes (Chain and Kemp 1934). In the case of nanoparticles, the positive charge of chitosan accounted for the positive zeta potential of the nanoparticles (Alomrani et al. 2019). Although a threshold of ± 30 mV is often used to indicate strong electrostatic stabilization of nanoparticles (Manaia et al. 2017), zeta potential values between -10 mV and $+10$ mV are generally considered indicative of nearly neutral (uncharged) liposomes (Wang et al. 2020). The zeta potential values observed in this study exceeded ± 10 mV, suggesting that the formulations possessed moderate stability, which is acceptable for liposomal and nanoparticle systems.

As hydrophilic macromolecules, these components can be efficiently incorporated into the aqueous core of both liposomes and nanoparticles. Moreover, the inclusion of PEG-lipids increases the polarity of P-LI vesicle bilayers, en-

Figure 4. CLSM images of skin treated with BSA-FITC-loaded P-LI MN patch for 8 h: (A) X–Y images (10 \times objective lens). The images are divided into four parts: 1, red fluorescence of Rh-probed P-LI; 2, green fluorescence of BSA-FITC; 3, bright-field image; 4, overlay of 1 and 2. (B) X–Y serial images (10 \times objective lens), with the white arrow indicating the microneedle insertion site and the blue arrow indicating the follicular duct. (C) Ortho image. (D) Fluorescence intensity profile of Rh (red)-probed P-LI and BSA-FITC (green)-loaded P-LI MN patch at different skin depths.

hancing the entrapment of hydrophilic compounds (Rangsimawong et al. 2014). Consequently, the high entrapment efficiency of GP extract in P-LI vesicles supports its suitability for PEGylated lipid nanocarrier-based delivery and highlights its potential therapeutic efficacy. Additionally, the GP extract-loaded P-LI formulation was able to be in-

corporated into the MN patch. The combined application of P-LI nanoencapsulation technology and the minimally invasive MN technique offers a synergistic approach that effectively overcomes the inherent skin barrier, facilitating enhanced transport of bioactive macromolecules from GP extract into and across the skin and hair follicles.

To investigate skin permeation, BSA-FITC was employed as a model macromolecular protein in nanocarriers due to its well-characterized properties. SDS-PAGE analysis of water-soluble proteins from GP crude extracts revealed bands at 66, 37, 24, 20, and ~10 kDa, corresponding to albumin, glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate dehydrogenase, trypsinogen, trypsin inhibitor, and polypeptides, respectively. Thus, BSA (66 kDa) serves as an appropriate surrogate for approximating the loading and behavior of GP proteins and growth factors in nanocarrier systems (Tansathien et al. 2022). Hydrophilic macromolecules, including proteins, growth factors, and amino acids, experience limited passive penetration through the skin. The stratum corneum, the outermost barrier of the skin, comprises a lipophilic layer that restricts passive diffusion, allowing only small, potent, and moderately lipophilic molecules to penetrate deeper skin layers (Kalluri and Banga 2011). This study developed macromolecular protein-loaded nanocarriers for delivering proteins and growth factors across the skin. Skin permeation of entrapped polymeric nanoparticles (NP and P-NP) after 8 h was significantly lower than that of the BSA-FITC solution, attributed to the critical role of drug release rates from these nanoparticles in determining their effectiveness. Chitosan functions as the matrix in drug-loaded nanoparticles, providing advantages crucial to transdermal delivery, such as sustained and controlled release, adhesion promotion, and biocompatibility (Ma et al. 2022).

Surface-modified liposomes have demonstrated effectiveness in encapsulating biomacromolecular agents, including amino acids, peptides, and proteins derived from deer antler velvet. This encapsulation strategy ensures efficient delivery and enhanced safety (Rangsimawong et al. 2024a). P-LI vesicles further improve skin permeability to entrapped hydrophilic substances. Liposomal architecture provides a protective environment for these hydrophilic compounds, and the presence of PEG-lipids increases membrane polarity, enhancing incorporation efficiency. Furthermore, P-LI formulations containing an edge activator (polysorbate 20) form deformable vesicles capable of penetrating the stratum corneum intact, effectively transporting vesicle-bound drugs deeper into the skin (Rangsimawong et al. 2016). The PEG chains on the liposome surface also interact with stratum corneum lipids, leading to temporary disruption of the skin barrier and improved penetration of liposomal formulations and hydrophilic compounds (Luo et al. 2016). P-LI nanovesicles thus serve as a delivery system for hydrophilic macromolecules, facilitating their permeation and deposition within the skin. Their ability to enhance BSA-FITC permeation through the skin, surpassing that of a simple solution, has been previously documented (Sanguanboonyaphong et al. 2024). However, lipid nanocarriers alone face limitations in achieving deep skin penetration due to their interaction with the stratum corneum's lipid structure (Rangsimawong et al. 2016). Therefore, a dual approach utilizing these nanovesicles with microneedling techniques was

developed to further improve transdermal permeation of biomacromolecules.

The microneedling technique was used to establish potential pathways for the transdermal delivery of macromolecules such as BSA (Demir et al. 2013; Han and Das 2013), ovalbumin (van der Maaden et al. 2014), and insulin (Lee et al. 2017; Ma et al. 2018). A previous study demonstrated that MN made from hyaluronic acid and PEG dimethacrylate exhibited favorable properties for skin application, with a progressive increase in the percentage of height reduction under applied forces ranging from 4.0 to 20.0 N. Notably, at the average applied force exerted by human thumbs (20 N), none of the polymeric microneedles displayed brittleness, highlighting patient safety. This MN patch offered a minimally invasive method to breach the stratum corneum barrier with an insertion depth of approximately 130 μm , presenting a promising delivery system for biomacromolecules into the epidermis and dermis. Complete dissolution of the MN in the skin was achieved within a 6 h insertion period (Tansathien et al. 2022). MNs have also demonstrated the ability to transport drug-encapsulated micro/nanoparticles, including nanoparticles (Zaid Alkilani et al. 2022), nanomicelles (Bao et al. 2021; Chen et al. 2021), and mesoporous silica particles (Wang et al. 2021), facilitating prolonged drug delivery through the skin (Nguyen and Nguyen 2023). The use of nanoparticle-integrated microneedles enables sustained release of macromolecules (Oh and Jung 2022).

The skin penetration pathways were visualized using the CLSM technique. Upon absorption onto the skin surface, P-LI vesicles release their entrapped compounds, which then partition into the skin layers (Rangsimawong et al. 2014). The minimally invasive MN system creates micropores in the skin, bypassing the stratum corneum barrier. This MN-assisted delivery facilitated the co-penetration of hydrophilic macromolecules and lipid-based nanocarriers into the viable epidermis, upper dermis, and hair follicles. Therefore, the P-LI MN patch shows strong potential as a transdermal and transfollicular delivery system for biomacromolecules from GP extract.

In the context of transdermal delivery of bioactive macromolecular proteins, degradation by proteolytic enzymes within the skin may occur. Nevertheless, previous studies have reported that cutaneous proteolytic activity is relatively low compared with mucosal routes, reducing the likelihood of extensive protein degradation (Steinstrasser and Merkle 1995). In this study, no apparent protein degradation was observed, as indicated by the visual similarity in color between the permeated medium and the extract and the detection of fluorescently labeled protein in the receiver medium. Future studies will therefore include post-permeation protein integrity assays to confirm the stability of the delivered proteins. In addition, while previous reports indicate that GP extract does not cause notable adverse effects (Sanguanboonyaphong et al. 2024), comprehensive *in vivo* safety evaluations remain necessary to confirm the tolerability and safety of these formulations before clinical translation.

Conclusion

This study successfully loaded GP extract into a novel system combining PEGylated lipid nanocarriers (P-LI) with MN. This dual approach significantly enhanced the transdermal delivery of macromolecular proteins. Visualization of skin permeation pathways confirmed the delivery of these proteins into both the skin and hair follicles, achieving maximum penetration depth and intensity. The successful integration of P-LI nanocarriers and MN proved instrumental in improving the skin permeability of the loaded compounds, establishing a highly promising transdermal delivery system for hydrophilic macromolecules derived from placenta extracts.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

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The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

Experiments on animals: Abdominal porcine skins were sourced from intrapartum stillborn animals at a local farm in Sisaket Province, Thailand, with approval from the Investigational Review Board (05/2565/IACUC), Animal Experimentation Ethics Committee, Ubon Ratchathani University.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

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Author contributions

Worranan Rangsimawong: conceptualization, methodology, visualization, funding acquisition, writing – original draft preparation; Sureewan Duangjit: methodology, investigation, writing – review and editing; Ponwanit Charoenputtakun: methodology; Kritsanaporn Tansathien: methodology, investigation; Tanasait Ngawhirunpat: supervision; Praneet Opanasopit: supervision.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text or Supplementary Information.

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Supplementary material 1

Supplementary tables

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Data type: docx

Explanation note: **table S1.** Particle size ranges of nanocarrier formulations. **table S2.** Stability of P-LI formulations at conditions of 4 °C, 25 °C and 40 °C for initial day and 90 days.

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